

Supplementary Material

The following figures provide additional analyses supporting the robustness, interpretability, and performance of the XGBoost–Cox survival model for pediatric adrenocortical tumors. These include bootstrap- and cross-validation–based assessments of the tumor volume cut-off, feature importance stability, model performance across varying sample sizes, calibration at clinically relevant time points, and dependence plots for key predictors. Together, these supplementary results further demonstrate the consistency and transparency of the proposed model.

Figure S1. Nested cross-validation performance.

Distribution of C-indices obtained from 10-fold nested cross-validation. The mean C-index was 0.78 (range 0.70–0.90), confirming robust model performance.

Figure S2. Learning curve of the XGBoost–Cox model.

Learning curve demonstrating model performance (C-index) as a function of training set size. Performance stabilized after approximately 60% of the cohort was included, suggesting adequate sample size despite high variance in small subsets.

Figure S3. Bootstrap distribution of tumor volume cut-offs.

Histogram of tumor volume thresholds obtained from 500 bootstrap resamples. The median cut-off was approximately 190 mL, with the majority of estimates falling below 400 mL, indicating a robust signal for a low-volume risk threshold.

Figure S4. Empirical cumulative distribution (ECDF) of bootstrap cut-offs.

Cumulative distribution function of bootstrap-derived cut-offs ($n = 500$). The curve illustrates that 75% of estimates remained below 250 mL.

Figure S5. Tumor volume cut-off distribution in repeated cross-validation.

Violin plots showing tumor volume cut-offs derived across repeated 5×5 cross-validation resampling. Results confirm consistency of the bootstrap-derived threshold around 190 mL.

Figure S6. Bootstrap stability of feature importance (mean SHAP values ± SD).

Feature importance derived from SHAP values across 500 bootstrap iterations. Tumor volume and metastatic status were consistently the most influential predictors, followed by pT stage and resection status.

Figure S7. SHAP dependence of tumor volume, stratified by metastatic status.

Dependence plot showing the monotonic increase in predicted risk with tumor volume. Color indicates metastatic status (cM0 vs. cM1). The risk contribution of tumor volume was not significantly altered by metastatic status.

Figure S8. Calibration plot at 1 year (independent test set).

Calibration of predicted vs. observed survival at 1 year in the independent test set (n = 20). Predictions show acceptable alignment with observed outcomes, though precision is limited by small sample size.

Figure S9. Calibration plot at 3 years (independent test set).

Calibration of predicted vs. observed survival at 3 years in the independent test set (n = 20).

Observed agreement was reasonable but interpretation remains limited due to small numbers.